

THE CURRENT STATE OF USING EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN THE MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: In this article, the goals and tasks of the native language teaching methodology course, the role of vocabulary in literacy teaching and the current situation in schools, and the role and methods in developing students' speech and forming a creative thinker. stated. At the same time, methods of applying scientific-theoretical information to practice have been revealed.

Key word: lexicology, lexicology, educational dictionary, lexicography, need, textbook, program, creative thinking.

National independence opened a new page in the history of our republic. Uzbekistan became known to the world as a developed country in a short period of time; In the world community, attention to its culture, history, artifacts, customs, and language has also increased. The fact that the Uzbek language has an official status as a state language has increased its social value and expanded the scope of its use. This required his education to improve the culture of practical use of the language.

Today, the pace of development in all aspects of our social lifestyle has accelerated tremendously, intellectual potential, high thinking has become the main condition for survival in the world, the development of science and technology has unexpectedly increased, and human spirituality, which ensures the preservation of the nation as a people, the nation as a nation. It is no secret that human society is fundamentally different from the times it has experienced so far. In such conditions, it is clear that the demand for education, especially the teaching of the mother tongue, is more serious than ever. After all, it is not easy to attract the attention of the learner, to direct his mental and physical activity correctly and purposefully in the era of globalization and the age of the Internet. The abundance and variety of information sources and their daily improvement, scope and scope are expanding, making it extremely convenient and modern, interesting and necessary for the student in the educational process, and at the same time, in a way that is easy and fast to reach. requires information to be provided. Without them, it is impossible to think about achieving the desired result.

In such a situation, the young generation can resist various spiritual threats, a culture of reading has been formed, they understand the true nature of the realities happening around them, they think creatively and express their thoughts independently, fluently and accurately in various speech situations in oral/written forms. It is our main task to raise people so that they can express their feelings.

It is known to many that during the former regime, the main role was given to students, but there was a problem of not allowing them to think independently and creatively. Accordingly, in the first years of independence, there was a need to fundamentally reform the system of education, science, and vocational training across the country, relying on the experience of developed countries of the world, and innovations of state importance, first of all, education started from the system. The Law "On Education" and the development of the State National Program for the Development of School Education were related to this. The state, as the main reformer, is committed to linguistics ("creating excellent academic and educational grammars that fully reflect the original nature and characteristics of the Uzbek language, creating dictionaries and encyclopedias, brochures and textbooks on various topics and directions) to teach the mother tongue ("who expresses his opinion correctly and fluently orally and in writing, has a culture of reading, is able to think independently and creatively, understands the opinions of others - communication and speech development of a person with a developed culture") set the next tasks.

The main goal of school mother tongue education is to develop the student's abilities to think creatively, logically, creatively, figuratively and associatively, to express the product of thinking in oral and written form correctly and fluently in accordance with the conditions of speech. As can be seen from the State requirements for education at the lower levels of continuous education, a new era in language policy has begun in our country.

Well, under such conditions, it is difficult for us to give a positive answer to the question of the current state of using educational dictionaries in the mother tongue classes of secondary general education schools.

As we mentioned, the role of dictionaries in the educational system is incomparable. The requirement of the era for mother tongue education in school is creative thinking, creative thinking, i.e. "Through mother tongue education, the student is able to think as a student, to understand the opinion of others, to express his opinion in oral and written form. A lot of research is being done on ways to fulfill this task in order to develop a person with developed speech

(communicative) competence aimed at being able to express correctly and fluently in accordance with speech conditions. In all of them, the qualification requirements of the general secondary education in the native language are analyzed.

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